

Therapeutic approaches and complications in the treatment of precancerous changes of the cervix

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Abstract

Cervical cancer is one of the leading socially significant diseases among the female population, classified as the second most common cause of morbidity and mortality in women worldwide. Timely detection and treatment of precancerous changes of the cervix will help reduce these rates and is also one of the main mechanisms for addressing this public health problem. This article presents and analyzes the therapeutic approaches and their complications in the treatment of precancerous changes of the cervix in Bulgaria.

Keywords

cancer, cervix, complications, precancerous changes, therapeutic approaches

Introduction

Cervical cancer (CRC) is a major public health problem, classified as the second most common cause of morbidity and mortality in women worldwide after breast cancer. The lack of, or inadequate, screening programs, as well as limited access to health services in some regions of the world, explains the large geographical differences in cervical cancer rates.

Timely detection and treatment of precancerous changes of the cervix among the female population will help to reduce the morbidity and mortality caused by cervical cancer. The incidence of premalignant changes in the cervix varies widely worldwide and is directly dependent on the availability of an effectively functioning screening program for cervical cancer (Macgregor 1994). It is reported in the literature that 6–10% of the screening population for cervical cancer with an abnormal result from cytological

examination proceed to colposcopy with subsequent biopsy, in which 25–30% are found to have precancerous changes in the cervix (French 2004; Javanbakht 2023). The most commonly used definition of “pre-malignant changes in the cervix” is changes in the cells that, in the long term, may lead to the development of cancer. Precancerous lesions of the cervix are changes in the cells of the cervix in an area called the transformation zone (Tsehay 2020).

Several terms are used in the literature to describe precancerous cellular changes in the cervix, the most common of which is cervical intraepithelial neoplasia (CIN), which is classified as mild dysplasia – CIN1; moderate dysplasia – CIN2; and severe dysplasia – CIN3. Also commonly used is the term squamous intraepithelial lesion (SIL).

According to the World Health Organization (WHO), these changes can exist at any of three stages: cervical intraepithelial neoplasia stage 1 (CIN1), stage 2 (CIN2), or

stage 3 (CIN3). These conditions are not yet cancer, but if left untreated, CIN2 or CIN3—collectively called cervical intraepithelial neoplasia stage 2 plus (CIN2+)—can progress to cervical cancer (Guidelines for screening and treatment of precancerous lesions for cervical cancer prevention WHO guidelines 2013; Panjković 2008).

Human papillomavirus (HPV) infection is the leading etiological factor in the development of premalignant and malignant diseases of the cervix. HPVs are non-enveloped DNA viruses with a tropism for squamous epithelium. Virus-induced oncogenesis is the result of the interaction between viral oncoproteins E6 and E7 and tumor suppressor host genes p53 and Rb. According to their oncogenic potential, HPVs are divided into three groups: viruses with low, medium, and high oncogenic risk (Cooper 2025). Viral infection can be latent and productive.

Before HPV was identified as the causative agent, research—alongside investigations into sexual behavior and sexually transmitted infections (STIs)—identified social and environmental factors such as parity, oral contraceptive use, smoking, a weakened immune system, chlamydial infection, and obesity as risk factors for invasive cervical cancer. Because HPV is present in almost all cervical tumors, other risk determinants cannot be considered independent of HPV infection. However, because HPV infection alone is not sufficient to lead to the development of invasive cervical cancer or its precursors, other agents must be involved in the carcinogenic process. Thus, current epidemiological research focuses on identifying factors that influence whether HPV infection will resolve spontaneously or progress to malignancy. Environmental factors, once thought to play an independent role in cervical carcinogenesis, are now being investigated as potential cofactors mediating the central role of HPV. Epidemiological studies have focused on the role of dietary factors and serum trace elements in the etiology of invasive cervical cancer as predictive factors. Studies on the risks of CIN and invasive cervical cancer are relatively consistent, showing protective effects from the consumption of fruits and vegetables, beta-carotene, and vitamins A, C, and E (Brock 1998; Van Eenwyk 1991, 1992; Liu 1993). Other nutrients that have been inversely associated with cervical cancer risk include lycopene and tocopherols (Palan 1996; Kwasniewska 1997). There is high biological plausibility for a protective effect of diet in the genesis of cervical neoplasia. Carotenoids, tocopherols, and ascorbic acid are potent antioxidants capable of scavenging intracellular reactive radicals, thereby preventing potential DNA damage. Beta-carotene, in particular, may have the additional beneficial property of being a metabolic precursor of retinoic acid, which works by modulating epithelial cell growth and differentiation. Dietary factors may also play a role in cervical immunity (Cox 1995; Potischman 1996).

The approaches and methods of treatment for precancerous changes in the cervix vary greatly in different parts of the world.

Conservative outpatient approaches to the treatment of cervical dysplasia are common in industrialized countries,

while in developing countries, invasive inpatient methods such as conization and hysterectomy are still mainly relied upon. Outpatient therapy using methods such as diathermocoagulation, laser ablation, cryotherapy, and loop electrosurgical excision procedure (LEEP), combined with appropriate follow-up, is suitable for the management of visible lesions of the ectocervix when invasive cancer and endocervical involvement have been ruled out. These methods are effective (80–95% cure rate), have few side effects, are simple, and are inexpensive. The cure rate varies depending on the method used and the severity of the lesions.

The most commonly used types of ablative treatment for precancerous changes of the cervix in Bulgaria are diathermocoagulation of precancerous changes of the cervix and laser ablation of precancerous changes of the cervix.

Diathermocoagulation is mainly used to treat cervical intraepithelial neoplasia (CIN) 1, 2, or 3. It is also used for persistent infection with high-risk types of human papillomavirus (HPV). This procedure is usually chosen because of its effectiveness, ease of implementation, and the possibility of performing it in an outpatient setting and with limited resources (Chansen 1971). Diathermocoagulation also has some disadvantages, the main ones being the following:

Pain and discomfort: Although the procedure is usually performed under local anesthesia, some women may experience pain and discomfort during and after the procedure.

Risk of infection: As with any surgical procedure, there is a risk of infection. It is important to follow the instructions for postoperative care to minimize this risk.

Bleeding: Mild bleeding may occur after the procedure, which is usually temporary. In rare cases, additional medical intervention may be necessary.

Scarring and narrowing of the cervix: In some cases, scarring may form, leading to narrowing of the cervix. This may affect future pregnancies and deliveries.

Need for repeat procedures: Sometimes a repeat procedure may be necessary if the affected area has not fully healed after the initial intervention (De Punzio 1984; La Vecchia 1986).

Laser ablation of the cervix requires specific equipment to ensure that the procedure is both effective and safe. The main components are a laser device, a colposcope, a speculum with or without an integrated HEC connector, and a device for extracting the HEC smoke (del Valle Rubido 2019).

Laser ablation of the cervix is primarily used to treat various cervical conditions such as cervical intraepithelial neoplasia (CIN) 1, 2, or 3; genital warts (condylomas)—effectively removing warts caused by the human papillomavirus (HPV); and postcoital bleeding caused by benign lesions of the cervix (del Valle Rubido 2019). Although effective in treating abnormal cervical cells, laser ablation has some disadvantages and potential side effects:

- **Lack of tissue for histology:** Unlike excisional procedures, laser ablation does not provide a tissue sample for histological examination, which can be important in confirming the diagnosis and ensuring that all abnormal cells have been removed.

- Bleeding: Some patients may experience bleeding during or after the procedure.
- Infection: There is a risk of infection after the procedure.
- Scarring: The procedure may cause scarring of the cervical tissue.
- Cervical stenosis: In rare cases, the procedure may result in cervical stenosis, which is a narrowing of the cervical canal.
- Discomfort and pain: Patients may experience mild to moderate pain and discomfort, similar to menstrual cramps.
- Vaginal discharge: A watery discharge is common after the procedure.
- Fatigue: Some patients report fatigue after the procedure.
- High cost of the equipment.

The purpose of this article is to present, analyze, and compare therapeutic approaches for the treatment of precancerous changes of the cervix in Bulgaria.

To achieve this goal, the following TASKS were set and studied:

- To analyze anamnestic, clinical, laboratory, and other data regarding the general health status of the main groups of the studied patients.
- Based on cytological and colposcopic findings, to study the condition of the cervical epithelium in the studied groups of women.
- To evaluate the results of the treatment of precancerous changes of the cervix with diathermocoagulation, with follow-up at 3, 6, and 12 months after the therapeutic procedure.
- To evaluate the results of the treatment of precancerous changes of the cervix with laser ablation, with follow-up at 3, 6, and 12 months after the therapeutic procedure.

Materials and methods

The present study is prospective and was conducted during the period from December 2019 to December 2024. The subject of the study was a selected group of 265 women aged between 18 and 59 years. The DTC procedures were performed in the Onco-Prophylactic Office of the DKB of SBALAG „Maichin Dom“ – Sofia, and the laser ablations in MC „Dr. Gunev“.

In connection with the implementation of the goal and the tasks set, the patients were divided into the following clinical groups:

Group I (first group): women with a histological result of CIN 2, in whom DTC of the cervical canal was performed ($n = 131$).

Group II (second group): women with a histological result of CIN 2, in whom laser ablation of the cervical canal was performed ($n = 134$).

Patients from the two groups did not have significant differences in age, general clinical condition, severity of colposcopic findings, or cytological and histological results.

A wide range of sociological and documentary methods were used in the study, as well as the following statistical methods:

1. Descriptive statistical methods.

Categorical variables are presented as absolute (n) and/or relative frequencies (%). Quantitative variables are presented as median and interquartile range (IQR: 25th and 75th percentiles) due to their non-Gaussian distribution, supplemented with a simple range (minimum and maximum). Quantitative variables with up to four values are also treated as ordinal categorical variables.

2. Analytical statistical methods.

The shape of the distribution was assessed using the Kolmogorov–Smirnov test. Relationships between categorical variables were assessed with chi-square analysis (Fisher's exact test, when applicable).

Mean values of two groups were compared using the Mann–Whitney test.

Differences between ordinal variables at two time points were assessed with the Wilcoxon test. To identify factors of binary events, logistic regression analysis was applied.

Results with p -values < 0.05 were considered statistically significant.

Quantitative analyses were performed using the statistical software package SPSS 17.0. Microsoft Office products were used for tabular and graphical processing and presentation.

Results and discussion

To carry out any analytical process, a large amount of primary, reliable information is required, collected through the main sociological and epidemiological sources and methods. After statistical processing of the collected primary descriptive information and its transformation into aggregate prescriptive data, the analysis shows that in the entire cohort, the average age of the patients is 30.9 years, and the median is 29 (IQR 24–35). In the two groups defined by the applied therapy, no statistically significant difference in age was demonstrated ($p = 0.065$), although patients who underwent laser ablation were slightly younger (median 29) than those treated with DTC (median 31). However, the difference was not significant (Table 1).

For the purposes of the study, we compared the two groups according to their reproductive status, i.e., by the relative proportion of women with pregnancies, women who had given birth, women with abortions, and women in menopause. As is evident from the data in Table 2, no statistically significant differences were observed ($p > 0.05$) with respect to the applied therapy.

Table 1. Age of patients in both groups according to the therapy administered.

THERAPY	DTK	Mean	31.9
		Median	31.0
		Percentile 25	25.0
		Percentile 75	39.0
	Laser ablation	Mean	29.9
		Median	29.0
		Percentile 25	24.0
		Percentile 75	33.0

Table 2. Distribution in the two groups according to reproductive status.

		THERAPY				P
		DTK		Laser ablation		
		n	%	n	%	
pregnancies	No	68	52.3%	81	60.0%	0.207
	Yes	62	47.7%	54	40.0%	
births	No	71	54.6%	87	64.4%	0.103
	Yes	59	45.4%	48	35.6%	
menopause	No	6	4.6%	3	2.2%	0.327
	Yes	124	95.4%	132	97.8%	
abortions	No	118	90.8%	125	92.6%	0.591
	yes	12	9.2%	10	7.4%	

We followed, separately for both patient groups, the changes in the dynamics of the examinations between the first, third, sixth, and twelfth months. Due to the small number of histologies performed at 3, 6, and 12 months, these were excluded from the analysis. As shown in Table 3, a significant improvement in the Pap smear was observed in both groups between 1 and 3 months ($p < 0.001$). The improvement continued between 3 and 6 months in both groups ($p = 0.004$ for DTC and $p = 0.002$ for laser ablation). However, between 6 and 12 months, no further improvement was observed in either group ($p > 0.05$). In summary, both groups showed significant improvement in the Pap smear between 1 and 12 months ($p < 0.001$).

Table 3. Comparison of the two groups by results of the Pap smear and colposcopic examination at 1, 3, 6, and 12 months.

	THERAPY			
	DTC		Laser ablation	
	Z	p	Z	p
3m. ЦН - 1 ЦН	-9.878 ^b	$p < 0.001$	-10.127 ^b	$p < 0.001$
6m. ЦН - 3m. ЦН	-2.887 ^b	0.004	-3.051 ^b	0.002
12m. ЦН - 6m. ЦН	0.000 ^c	1.000	0.000 ^c	1.000
12m. ЦН - 1 ЦН	-10.074 ^b	$p < 0.001$	-10.239 ^b	$p < 0.001$
3m. Colpo find - 1 Colposcopic finding	-10.217 ^b	$p < 0.001$	-10.361 ^b	$p < 0.001$
6m. Colpo - 3m. Colpo find	-2.449 ^d	0.014	-1.342 ^d	0.180
12m. Colpo find - 6m. Colpo	-1.732 ^d	0.083	-1.414 ^d	0.157
12m. Colpo find - 1 Colposcopic find	-10.093 ^b	0.000	-10.283 ^b	0.000

Regarding the dynamics of the colposcopic examination, both groups demonstrated significant improvement between 1 and 3 months ($p < 0.001$), and further improvement between 3 and 6 months was observed only in the group treated with DTC ($p = 0.014$). Between 6 and 12 months, no significant changes were noted in either group ($p > 0.05$). In sum-

mary, both groups exhibited significant improvement in the colposcopic findings between 1 and 12 months ($p < 0.001$).

Too few patients had a test for human papillomavirus; therefore, no temporal comparison was conducted.

To achieve the objectives of this study, we evaluated the results and complications of the treatment of precancerous changes of the cervix using diathermocoagulation and laser ablation, with follow-up at 3, 6, and 12 months after the therapeutic procedure. The most common complications associated with these procedures—described in the introduction—are discomfort, pain, and bleeding following treatment. As shown in Table 4, no statistically

Table 4. Complications of DTC and laser ablation.

		THERAPY				P
		DTC		Laser ablation		
		n	%	n	%	
Discomfort after the procedure	Yes, a few hours	55	42.3%	53	39.6%	0.620
	Yes, a few days	11	8.5%	9	6.7%	
	Yes, a week	1	0.8%	0	0.0%	
	Yes, a month or longer	0	0.0%	0	0.0%	
	Yes, it persists.	0	0.0%	0	0.0%	
pain after the procedure	No	63	48.5%	72	53.7%	0.569
	Yes, a few hours	23	17.7%	22	16.4%	
	Yes, a few days	1	0.8%	0	0.0%	
	Yes, a week	0	0.0%	0	0.0%	
	Yes, a month or longer	0	0.0%	0	0.0%	
bleeding after the procedure	Yes, it persists.	0	0.0%	0	0.0%	0.870
	No	106	81.5%	112	83.6%	
	Yes, a few hours	21	16.2%	23	17.2%	
	Yes, a few days	6	4.6%	7	5.2%	
	Yes, a week	7	5.4%	7	5.2%	
	Yes, a month or longer	0	0.0%	0	0.0%	
	Yes, it persists.	16	12.3%	11	8.2%	
	No	80	61.5%	86	64.2%	

significant differences were found between the two groups in terms of the three reported complications ($p > 0.05$).

Approximately half of the patients in both groups did not experience any discomfort after the procedure. However, 42.3% of those treated with DTC and 39.6% of those treated with laser ablation reported discomfort lasting for several hours, while 8.5% and 6.7%, respectively, reported discomfort lasting for several days.

The majority of patients (over 80% in both groups) reported no pain. Pain lasting several hours was experienced by 17.7% of those in the DTC group and 16.4% in the laser ablation group. One patient (0.8%) in the DTC group reported pain lasting several days.

More than 60% of patients in both groups did not experience bleeding after the procedure. Bleeding for several hours was reported by 16.2% of those treated with DTC and 17.2% with laser ablation; bleeding for several days was reported by 4.6% and 5.2%, respectively; bleeding for one week was reported by 5.4% and 5.2%, respectively; and persistent bleeding was reported by 12.3% and 8.2% of patients in the DTC and laser ablation groups, respectively.

Since persistent bleeding is considered a serious complication, we investigated potential risk factors associated with

it. The entire sample was analyzed collectively, and based on the data (Table 5), we found that the risk of bleeding increases with higher educational level, lower employment, later menarche, shorter menstrual cycle length and duration, fewer pregnancies, earlier onset of sexual activity, as well as the presence of cervical lesions, human papillomavirus (HPV) infection, and more severe colposcopic findings.

With the factors thus identified, we ran a multiple model using the sequential inclusion method to eliminate insignificant variables. The results were then adjusted for age. We found that each level of education above the average increased the risk of persistent bleeding by 2.4 times. A shorter menstrual cycle increased the risk by 3.3 times for each day. Early onset of sexual activity increased the risk by 2.4 times for each year. A worsening colposcopic finding increased the risk by 3.6 times for each level (Table 6; Fig. 1).

Table 5. Risk factors for persistent bleeding.

	p	OR	95% C.I.	
education	0.005	1.788	1.192	2.681
employment	0.027	1.302	1.031	1.643
Menarche	0.001	1.941	1.295	2.911
MC length	0.082	0.812	0.643	1.027
Duration of MC	<0.001	0.416	0.270	0.639
number of pregnancies	0.048	0.486	0.237	0.994
Beginning of sex- age	0.002	0.530	0.355	0.793
Cervical Wound	0.042	2.462	1.035	5.859
1 HPV	0.066	6.829	0.884	52.782
1 Colposcopic finding	0.001	4.093	1.846	9.076

Table 6. Factors for persistent bleeding.

	p	OR	95% C.I.	
education	0.012	2.388	1.210	4.711
duration of MC	0.001	0.301	0.148	0.610
beginning of sex (age)	0.001	0.411	0.239	0.706
1 Colposcopic finding	0.014	3.629	1.297	10.154

Figure 1. ROC curve of education.

Inferences and conclusion

Based on the analysis of this empirical study on therapeutic approaches and complications in the treatment of precancerous changes of the cervix, we conclude that in Bulgaria—classified as a developed socio-economic country according to the UN—highly effective conservative outpatient approaches for the treatment of cervical dysplasia have been implemented, namely diathermocoagulation and laser ablation. The analysis of the data showed that the main complication following these procedures is persistent bleeding. The probability of this complication increases with the level of education of the female population. Other major risk factors include the shorter duration of the menstrual cycle and the early onset of sexual activity.

In view of the trends in the main medico-demographic indicators used to assess public health in developed countries—namely decreasing birth rates, increasing life expectancy, and an aging population with a regressive age structure—and in order to reduce morbidity and mortality among women from this public health problem, namely cervical cancer, targeted efforts are needed by health authorities to organize preventive programs for precancerous changes in the cervix. These efforts should include primary prevention, aimed at eliminating carcinogenic and predisposing factors, and secondary prevention, focused on the early detection of malignant tumors or precancerous change. Another essential approach to reducing the negative health consequences of this socially significant disease is to strengthen health education among adolescents. This can be achieved through the introduction of health education programs in schools to promote health and prevent exposure to the identified risk factors. Such efforts will require coordinated and targeted action from both health and educational institutions.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Use of AI

No use of AI was reported.

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Author contributions

All authors have contributed equally.

Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

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